

Examining Fiscal Responsibility and Public Service Delivery in Local Government Councils of Rivers State

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This study examined the relationship between fiscal responsibility and public service delivery in local government councils in Rivers State. Fiscal transparency and fiscal accountability were used to measure fiscal responsibility. Based on this, two hypotheses were formulated for this study. This study was underpinned by the Good Governance Framework Theory. The cross-sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. Population for this study comprise of employees from the twenty-three (23) Local Government Area. For the purpose of this study, one hundred and twenty-eight (128) employees were selected from twelve local government councils in Rivers State for this study. The simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of samples while the taro yamen was adopted in calculating the sample size for the study. Therefore, the sample for this study was ninety-seven (97) employees. A well-structured questionnaire was used in collecting data for this study. Out of the total ninety-seven (97) questionnaires that was distributed, only ninety-two (92) were retrieved and used for the study. The Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to ascertain the relationship between fiscal responsibility and public service delivery in local government area of Rivers State. Findings for the study showed a positive and significant relationship between fiscal transparency and public service delivery in local government councils and fiscal accountability and public service delivery in local government councils in Rivers State. The study therefore concludes that both fiscal transparency and fiscal accountability are significantly associated with public service delivery. These findings underscore the importance of transparency and accountability in governance processes to achieve better outcomes for citizens.

Keywords: Fiscal Responsibility; Fiscal Transparency; Fiscal Accountability; Public Service Delivery

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important and enduring competitive advantages that a country can have in this era of globalization is an effective, dynamic and responsive public service (Olatona & Philip, 2015). Public service delivery is of profound importance to development, with governments and international organizations consistently emphasizing the need to improve their quality to boost the quality of life of the citizenry. The Nigerian public service is the most critical instrument of the modern state

for the effective and efficient public service delivery. It is saddled with the responsibility of implementing government policies and programmes for the attainment of sustainable development. The primary responsibility of any public service is to deliver services to citizens at affordable rate (Nife & Lawal, 2018). "*Public service delivery*" means the provision of affordable, accessible, qualitative and effective basic amenities to the citizens. Kimenyi and Shughart (2006) defined public services as those services such as national defence that are non-excludable, non-rival and indivisible both in production and consumption. Public services can be divided into two categories; social and economic services, social services

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consists of those services that yield benefits to the recipients, for instance health and education, while economic services are those services that generate returns to the provider; for example; housing, agriculture, transportation and communication network. Government also frequently intervenes in the delivery of improved public services that are only partially rival or partially excludable (controlled or restricted access services with extra taxes or levies), which are sometimes called semi-public service goods or services. Government service delivery is justified on the basis of equity and efficient delivery to the end users (Olatona & Philip, 2015).

Basic services, such as education and health care facilities are the responsibilities of the government and are systematically failing the people who need them most (i.e. the citizens). Sound education system and qualitative health care for example are all fundamental for human development and well-being. Yet public service providers are facing a lot of difficulties because of inadequate funding and mismanagement. For instance, funding is misappropriated, service providers do not report to work, building for schools and hospital equipment need repair, basic materials for the provision of good health and teaching devices are missing (Olatona & Philip, 2015).

Local governments play an essential role in providing services at grassroots levels. Such services delivered in various sectors may include agriculture, health, education, provision of portable water, and infrastructure (such as the construction and repair of feeder roads), (Liviga 2012). The realization and success of such activities by local governments requires effective mechanisms for accountability, transparency, and citizen participation in the provision of public services (Fadison, Bosco, Moses, & David, 2024). According to Nwoko, (2014), the challenge of corruption in Nigeria's public service led to the enactment of the Fiscal Responsibility Act 2007; to provide for prudent management of the nation's resources, ensure Long-term macro-economic stability of the national economy, secure greater accountability and transparency in fiscal operations within the Medium-Term Fiscal Policy Framework, and the establishment of the Fiscal Responsibility Commission. It is to ensure the promotion and enforcement of the nation's economic objectives as contained in chapter 2, section 16 of the constitution of Nigeria the Act that created the commission (Chris & Amujiri, 2015).

The Fiscal Responsibility Act (2007) ensures that the Federal Government carries out expenditure within formally specified and reasonable limits, given a sound revenue base. The new law also places strict limits on the accumulation of public debts. The FRA is designed to institutionalize transparency in the budgeting process in Nigeria, provide guidelines for public expenditure management and revenue forecasting, and limit the level of national debt. Collectively, these reforms should improve fiscal transparency on one hand, and the

efficiency of public expenditure, on the other. Given the scale of state corruption in Nigeria, the introduction of the FRA is a laudable step. However, the institutional and policy environment presents constraints for the effectiveness of the legislation, and there is the knotty issue of the fiscal and political privileges enjoyed by sub-national units in the Nigerian federation, and how the national political economy influences fiscal discipline (Ushie, 2010).

Fiscal responsibility provides for the necessary mechanisms and practices of managing nations resources in a prudent, transparent and accountable manner. It also include creating, optimizing and maintaining a balanced budget. According to Feingold (2004) in Yelwa (2014), fiscal responsibility is about balancing the budget and eliminating wasteful government spending. In a governmental context, a pledge of fiscal responsibility is a government's assurance that it will judiciously spend, earn, and generate funds without placing undue hardship on its citizens. It includes a moral contract to maintain a financially sound government for future generations on the understanding that a functional society is difficult to maintain without a financially secure government (Chris & Amujiri, 2015).

Fiscal Transparency and accountability advocacy arose from the belief that greater transparency and accountability can check corruption and inefficiency in public finance management by ensuring that public revenues are expended on developmental initiatives that will produce visible results (McGee & Gaventa, 2010). Transparency advocates maintain that greater access to government information is a sine-qua-non for greater accountability and better quality of government in the long term. Transparency promotes accountability and provides information to citizens about what their government is doing. Transparency thus makes information on existing conditions, decisions, and actions accessible, visible and understandable to all stakeholders (Otalor, Kankpang & Ayanbeshishie, 2023).

Thus this study adopts fiscal responsibility as a predictor of public service delivery. Fiscal responsibility is dimensioned by fiscal accountability and fiscal transparency.

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian Public Service is faced with a plethora of challenges, which have made the provision of essential services to the people to be inefficient and ineffective to the extent that the citizens are disappointed in the public service, which made them to keep wondering if they actually have government in their country (Egugbo, 2020). Corruption and mismanagement of public finances are problematic at all levels of government in Nigeria. Various forms of corruption such as theft, fraud, bribery,

extortion, requests for kickbacks, nepotism, and political patronage exist in Nigeria. At the sub-national level, however, the major driver of corruption is the discretionary use of funds by key government officers, with less emphasis on budgetary provisions and financial control measures in Local Government, Chairmen sometimes carryout orders of higher governments with little analysis of the impact of the expenditure on the budget and well-being of the people. The high level of fiscal profligacy at the sub-national level poses immense challenges for overall macroeconomic stability, debt management and public financial management (Ushie, 2010).

Researchers have examined various studies relating to fiscal responsibility and public service delivery e.g.: Adetoye, (2002); Adeyeye and Adeyeye, (2019), Agbatogun, (2019); Bauhr and Nasiritousi (2012); Nife and Lawal (2018); Ogoun and Ogoun (2012). Irrespective of the studies to the best of my knowledge no study have been able to establish the relationship between fiscal responsibility and public service delivery in Rivers state which had created a gap in literature which this study intends to fill.

Based on the above gap in literature, this study examined the relationship between fiscal responsibility and public

service delivery in Local Government Councils of Rivers State.

Aims and Objective of the Study

Generally, the aim and objectives of this study is to establish the relationship between fiscal responsibility and public service delivery. Specifically, this study intends to:

1. Examine the relationship between fiscal transparency and public service delivery in Local Government councils of Rivers State.
2. Establish the relationship between fiscal accountability and public service delivery in Local Government Councils of Rivers State.

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between fiscal transparency and public service delivery in Local Government Councils of Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between fiscal accountability and public service delivery in Local Government Councils of Rivers State.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Conceptualized by the Researcher

LITERATURE REVIEW

Fiscal Responsibility

Fiscal responsibility refers to deliberate plans, actions, processes and rules intended to ensure fiscal discipline, transparency and accountability in managing public funds and sustainable budget policy planning (Mihaela et al., 2020; Eden et al., 2013). It entails balancing the budget to obviate deficit spending and the burden on generations

yet unborn. It therefore, behooves any government to cut wasteful spending to ensure judicious use of taxpayers' money by putting in place, mechanisms for effective tracking of fiscal policy objectives and strategies (Otalor, Kankpang & Ayanbeshishie, 2023).

In an effort to streamline and ensure due processes in government expenditure, the fiscal responsibility Act 2007 was enacted by the Federal Government. The

Fiscal Responsibility Act (2007) ensures that the Federal Government carries out expenditure within formally specified and reasonable limits, given a sound revenue base. The new law also places strict limits on the accumulation of public debts. The FRA is designed to institutionalize transparency in the budgeting process in Nigeria, provide guidelines for public expenditure management and revenue forecasting, and limit the level of national debt (Chris & Amujiri, 2015).

Fiscal responsibility also relates to fiscal federalism. It is the assignment of revenue and expenditure functions to the different tiers of government, namely Central, State and Local Governments in a federal system of government. However, Fiscal Federalism and inter-governmental fiscal relations are often used interchangeably. Intergovernmental fiscal relations refer to the fiscal transactions and coordinating arrangements among the various tiers of government in a federation. The nature of intergovernmental fiscal relations constitutes an extremely relevant consideration for the attainment of fiscal nationality and macroeconomic stability in a federal structure of government (Chris & Amujiri, 2015).

Fiscal Transparency

Fiscal transparency refers to openness toward the public about government structure and functions, fiscal policy intentions, public sector accounts, and projections. It involves ready access to reliable, comprehensive, timely, understandable and internationally comparable information on government activities (Otalor, Kankpang & Ayanbeshishie, 2023). Fiscal transparency is a key element in the effective management of public finances, determining the fiscal risks, rational financial decision making, increasing accountability by policy makers, and improving fiscal policies.

In addition, fiscal transparency ensures openness of governments to the public about the structure and functions of governments, fiscal positions, potential risks, benefits versus costs of fiscal actions, and fiscal projections. It allows for a well-informed debate by both policymakers and the public about the design and results of fiscal policy, and provides legislatures, markets, and citizens with the information they need to hold governments' accountable. Furthermore, it helps to highlight risks to the fiscal outlook, allowing for earlier and smoother fiscal policy response to changing economic conditions and thereby reducing the incidence and severity of crises (Trenovski, Mangova, & Levkov, 2016).

Fiscal transparency, enables the electorate and financial markets to assess government financial position and the real costs and benefits of government activities, including their present and future economic and social implications (IMF, 2018, 2007; Kopits & Craig, 1998). In practice, fiscal transparency means that the public has a

right to know everything about public resources, including how funds are raised, managed, allocated and to what ends they are used. Furthermore, fiscal transparency is then required for the public to be able to judge the government's actual performance (Ferreira & Guerrero, 2022).

Fiscal Accountability

Accountability and responsibility are related terms that refer to an obligation to answer for actions taken in a relationship with others. According to United Nation Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA) 2013, "accountability is a relationship based on obligations to demonstrate, review, and take responsibility for performance, both the results achieved in light of agreed expectations and means." The term accountability is tenuous and elusive and lacks a precise definition (Otalor, Kankpang & Ayanbeshishie, 2023). According to Adegbite (2010) accountability is an obligation to demonstrate that work has been conducted in accordance with agreed rules and standards and the officer reports fairly and accurately on performance results vis-à-vis mandated roles and or/plans. Onochie (2001) sees accountability as "the duty to truthfully and transparently do one's duty and the obligation to allow access to information by which the quality of such services can be evaluated and being responsible and answerable to someone for some action (Agbatogun, 2019).

As cited in Otalor, Kankpang and Ayanbeshishie, (2023), financial accountability refers to the establishment of a series of control over revenue and expenditure of government to ensure that public monies have been used in the public interest. Administrative accountability entails a sound system of internal control (ethical codes, criminal penalties, and administrative reviews) that complements and ensures proper checks and balances supplied by constitutional government and an engaged citizenry. Political accountability entails free, fair and transparent elections where the people decide whether to retain or throw out incumbent officeholders by refusing to vote for such incumbents based on their performance in office. Social accountability is concerned with a wide range of citizen actions based on the exercise of their constitutionally guaranteed rights to hold the State to account for its actions (Ola & Effiong, 1999).

Public Service Delivery

The term public service is a term used in understanding the public sector. Public service can be used in two senses, first as an institution of government and second as service delivered by government. Adamolekun cited in Nwizu and Nwapi (2011) defines the public service as the "totality of services that are organized under government

authority. The notion of service delivery includes any interaction with the public sector in which users' citizens, residents, or businesses request or furnish data, manage their affairs, or carry out their activities. These services must be provided in a timely, predictable, dependable, and client-friendly manner.

The state is essential in the provision of a wide range of public services, from justice and security to services for private citizens and enterprises. In addition to traditional public services like healthcare and education, the provision of administrative services, such as the issuing of licenses and permissions, is governed by administrative proceedings (Fadison, Bosco, Moses, & David, 2024). To actualize this enormous task, public service emerged as the main machinery of government. Public service has therefore represented the building bridge for (government) to respond to the needs of the general public (citizens). In other words, public service carries the responsibility of formulating and executing policies and programs with the ultimate goal of delivering important welfare services that are capable of enhancing the standard of living of the general public.

Since the term "public" according to Jones (1970) refers to the citizens of a particular geography at a particular time, public service evokes the thought of government involvement in service delivery that is devoid of profit motives. Ogunna (2004) reiterates that the desire to satisfy the public through the implementation of public policies, enforcement of laws, and realization of public welfare culminates the effective public service delivery. Public service delivery becomes so paramount because it represents the fundamental structure of nation-building, it serves a tangible link between government and citizens to the government, and it also promotes the values of nations to the citizens and finally serves as a bond between the state and citizens (Walle and Scott 2009). Since effective service delivery remains the overall outcome of public services, measuring the performance to keep them in line of duty is very essential (Shittu, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

This study was underpinned by the Good Governance Framework. The World Bank first introduced the concept of Good Governance in its report titled *Governance and Development* in 1992. The report developed a set of principles and policies aimed to assist developing countries in governance. These principles include accountability, control, responsiveness, transparency, public participation, economy and efficiency.

In 1996, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) an Agency of the United Nations (UN) adopted eight (8) principles of good governance. These principles are participation, rule of law, consensus, equity and inclusiveness, effectiveness and efficiency,

accountability, transparency and responsiveness. Good governance framework in general sets some basic principles according to which government must run (Miogue, Polidan and Hulme, 1998).

Adherence to these principles will reveal that good governance is about how the public sector in third world countries will be responsive to the needs of the people, having realized that for a government to be regarded as good it, will not only be efficient, it must make accountability between the state and its citizens a core task (Bjork & Johansson, 2001). The exploration of good governance and its theory reveals the critical role of transparency, accountability, and citizen participation in effective governance. Despite facing challenges such as economic instability, political corruption, and security threats, there are opportunities for improvement through sound economic policies, institutional strengthening, and transparency measures. Embracing these principles and addressing challenges can help societies overcome governance obstacles and promote sustainable development and social progress (Ananyi, 2012). Good governance frameworks emphasize transparency, accountability, participation, and predictability as essential elements for effective governance and improved public service delivery. These frameworks highlight how fiscal responsibility contributes to these aspects of governance.

Empirical Review

Ngwakwe (2012), this article examines the link between financial accountability and service delivery. The methodological approach is conceptually rooted in reviews that culminate in suggested policy measures toward accountability and service delivery. The article discovers that service delivery problems are not unique to South Africa but a characteristic dominant in developing nations. The article finds that financial accountability is the sine qua none of effective service delivery and uncovers a number of factors that may limit accountability and hence service delivery. Similarly, Chris and Amujiri (2015) examined achieving fiscal responsibility for sustainable development in Nigeria: A contextual insight. The paper explores some theoretical issues surrounding fiscal responsibility in an economy. Major features of the fiscal responsibility laws in Nigeria are highlighted. Some of the fundamental flaws in Nigeria's public financial management that impede economic development as well as the imperatives of the fiscal responsibly law in Nigeria are analyzed. The paper concludes advisedly that strict adherence to the new fiscal policy law is bound to promote macroeconomic stability in Nigeria if strictly adhered to. Likewise, Kessy (2020) examined the extent to which fiscal transparency in Local Governments in Tanzania is practised and how this has played a greater role in service delivery. The study used a case study of

purposely selected local councils in Tanzania to examine the dynamics of fiscal transparency and service delivery. The findings show that there is little flow of information from higher levels of local governments to the lower levels in relation to resources available and results achieved. The information received from the councils is sometimes opaque or fuzzy in the sense that it does not reveal all about what their leaders do or what important decisions have been made about their councils. The study concludes that the importance of accountability and transparency attached to service delivery in any country is essential for good practice in local governance.

Moreso, Adeyeye, and Adeyeye (2019) examined the effect of fiscal accountability and transparency on service delivery in the Nigerian public sector. The study obtained usable data from 120 respondents through questionnaire from a sample size of 150 respondents selected randomly out of the population of 2,059 staff in five ministries in Lagos State, Nigeria. Furthermore, using convenience sampling method, 105 usable data were obtained from the consumers of services provided by these five ministries out of the 150 copies of questionnaire administered on them. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data. Findings from the study indicate that each of the individual independent variables has significant positive relationship with the dependent variable. The study also suggests that the combined effect of accountability and transparency appears to have greater effect on service delivery than any of the individual components. Furthermore, Agbatogun (2019) examined the impact of financial accountability and transparency on the management of public sector in Nigeria. Data were gathered primarily with the use of questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0.

The findings reveal that the level of governance in Nigeria is very poor due to various recent financial scandals and misappropriation of public funds the country has experienced over the years. Then again, Fadison, John-Bosco, Moses, and David (2024) investigates the relationship between financial accountability and service delivery in Kabale District Uganda. The study followed a cross sectional survey. Data from 86 respondents was collected and analyzed quantitatively, complemented with qualitative analysis. Since descriptive analysis entailed description of a single variable and its attributes, frequency tables were used to present the data. At the bivariate level, a Pearson correlation matrix was conducted to ascertain the relationships between the predictor variables and the dependent variable. A linear regression model was used to fit the data. Research findings from the regression model show that funds disbursement ($R=862$), auditing process ($R=656$) and records keeping systems ($R=899$) have a positive significance on the service delivery Kabale District local government. The main conclusion drawn from this

research is that funds disbursement, auditing process and record keeping systems have a significant effect on service delivery. Similarly, Nife and Lawal (2018) examined the practice of transparency and accountability in public sector and their attendant effects on service delivery. The paper found that lack of transparency and genuine accountability was responsible for poor and ineffective public service delivery. The paper suggested public enlightenment campaign, training and retraining of public servants, discipline, and the will to implement rules, as ways out of this ugly trend.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design: The cross-sectional survey design was adopted for the study because data was collected from single point in time.

Population of the Study: The target population comprises of employees from the twenty-three (23) Local Government Area of Rivers State. For the purpose of this study, one hundred and twenty-eight (128) senior employees on grade level 14 and above, were selected from twelve local government councils in Rivers State for this study.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size Determination: The simple random sampling technique was adopted in the selection of the sample for this study. The Taro Yamane's formula was employed to determine the sample size from the population. Therefore, the sample size for this study was ninety-seven (97).

Data Collection Method: Well-structured questionnaire was used to collect data for this study. Therefore, a total of ninety-seven (97) questionnaires were distributed for this study only nine-two (92) were used for the study which represent 95% of the total responses rate.

Validity and Reliability: The Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability of the statement items and analyses showed that all the items were above the benchmark of 0.70 while the validity of the research instrument was measured by the opinion of an expert in the field of management and supervisors.

Method of Data Analysis: The Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was deployed to test the relationship between fiscal responsibility and public service delivery in local government area of Rivers State, at 0.05 level of significance, with the aid of the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 24.0.

Demographic Analysis: The following information was provided by respondents: gender, age, and marital status.

Gender Distribution

Table 4.2 shows that 55 (60%) were males, while 37 (40%) of the respondents were females that participated

Gender of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
MALE	55	60.0	60.0	60.0
FEMALE	37	40.0	40.0	100.0
TOTAL	92	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Work, 2024

Age of Respondents

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
20-30 Years	0	0.0	0.0	0.0
31-40 Years	6	7.0	7.0	7.0
41-50 Years	37	40.0	40.0	47.0
51 Years and above	49	53.0	53.0	100.0
TOTAL	92	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 4.4: Marital Status of Respondents

MARITAL STATUS OF RESPONDENTS				
Marital Status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Single	15	16.0	16.0	16.0
Married	55	60.0	60.0	76.0
Others	22	24.0	24.0	100.0
TOTAL	92	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field Work, 2024

Table 4.5 Correlations between fiscal transparency and public services delivering

Correlations			
		Fiscal Transparency	Public Service Delivery
Fiscal Transparency	Pearson Correlation	1	.796**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	92	92
Public Service Delivery	Pearson Correlation	.796**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	92	92

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
Source: Survey Data, 2024

in this study. The analysis reveals that the respondents are mostly males.

Age of Respondents

Table 4.3 shows that the respondents are from the ages of 31 and above; none was below 30 years of age. Six of the respondents (7.0%) were between the age bracket of 31-40 years. Thirty-seven of the respondents (40.0%) were between the age bracket of 41-50 years. Forty-nine of the respondents (53.0%) were 50 years and above. Findings on the subjects' demographic profile also reveal that a large chunk of the study respondents are 41 years and above, with almost half of the respondents indicating

that they are forty plus in age. Table 4.4 reveals that 15 (16%) of the respondents are single, 55 (60%) of the respondents are married, while 22 (24%) of the respondents are divorced or did not want to disclose information regarding their marital status.

Test of Hypotheses

This section is concerned with the tests for the hypotheses. The result is based on correlations and it is a two-tailed test. The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient statistical analysis is used to test the correlations and strength of relations. The decision rule is to reject the null hypotheses where $p < 0.05$ significant

Table 4.6 Correlations between fiscal accountability and public service delivery

Correlations			
		Fiscal Accountability	Public Service Delivery
Fiscal Accountability	Pearson Correlation	1	.837**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.004
	N	92	92
Public Service Delivery	Pearson Correlation	.837**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	
	N	92	92

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data, 2024

level and accept the null hypotheses where $p > 0.05$. All bivariate hypotheses were tested in the null form.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between fiscal transparency and public service delivery

Relationship between fiscal transparency and public service delivery: The result of the data analysis shows a significant level $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$). The $r = 0.796$, showing strong positive correlation between the variables. The findings reveal a positive and significant relationship between the variables. Hence the null hypothesis is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between fiscal accountability and public service delivery.

Relationship between fiscal accountability and public service delivery: The result of the data analysis shows a significant level $p < 0.05$ ($0.004 < 0.05$). The $r = 0.837$, showing positive correlation between the variables. The findings reveal a positive relationship between the variables. Hence the null hypothesis is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The analyses showed that the fiscal transparency and accountability have significant relationship with public service delivery in local government area of River State. Fiscal transparency showed a significant and positive relationship with public service delivery showing a significant level $p < 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$) and the $r = 0.796$ while fiscal accountability showed a positive and significant relationship with public service delivery with a significant level $p < 0.05$ ($0.004 < 0.05$) and $r = 0.837$. The findings of this study suggest that when there is greater transparency in how public funds are managed and allocated, there tends to be an improvement in the delivery of public services.

Furthermore, transparency likely enables better

accountability, citizen trust, and more efficient allocation of resources, all of which contribute positively to public service outcomes. This implies that holding government officials accountable for the management of public finances leads to improved public service delivery. Accountability mechanisms such as audits, oversight, and reporting likely play a crucial role in ensuring that allocated funds are used effectively, thereby enhancing service delivery outcomes. The findings of this study is in line with the studies of Ngwakwe (2012); Kessy (2020); Adeyeye, and Adeyeye (2019); Fadison, John-Bosco, Moses, and David (2024); Nife and Lawal (2018).

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between fiscal responsibility and public service delivery in Rivers State Local Government Area. Two hypotheses were developed and examined. Fiscal transparency and fiscal accountability were adopted as proxies of fiscal responsibility which was used to examine their relationship on public service delivery. Findings from the study showed a positive and significant relationship between fiscal transparency and accountability and public service delivery. Based on the findings it can be concluded that both fiscal transparency and fiscal accountability are significantly associated with public service delivery. These findings underscore the importance of transparency and accountability in governance processes to achieve better outcomes for citizens.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion of this study, the following recommendations were proposed:

- i. Local Government Councils in Rivers State should implement policies that enhance fiscal transparency, such as open budget processes, regular financial reporting, and accessible public information on budget allocations and expenditures.

ii. Local Government Councils in Rivers State should strengthen the mechanisms for fiscal accountability, including independent audits, oversight by parliamentary bodies, and enforcement of penalties for financial mismanagement.

Suggestion for Further Research

i. Further research should explore specific mechanisms through which fiscal transparency and accountability influence public service delivery across different contexts or sectors.

ii. Moreso, further research should investigate the potential impact of transparency and accountability on specific public services (e.g., healthcare, education) to identify sector-specific best practices.

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